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Abstract

This study examines how the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes influences teacher efficacy and impacts students in Japan and India. Survey data was collected from 661 public elementary school teachers in Japan and 306 elementary school teachers in India. Using the "WISC-IV Guidance of Inclusive Education in Regular Classes" scale, the researchers performed a confirmatory factor analysis followed by a simultaneous multi-group analysis to evaluate cross-national similarities and differences. The results demonstrated that teachers in India achieved significantly higher scores in subfactors regarding personal teaching efficacy, understanding student family environments, and forming cohesive learning groups compared to their Japanese counterparts. Conversely, Japanese teachers exhibited greater variance in both personal and general educational efficacy. The findings indicate that collaborative support from parents improves teaching efficacy for Indian instructors, whereas Japanese educators may require additional systematic assistance to reinforce their professional efficacy.

Impact of Educational Guidance of Inclusive Education in Regular Classes and on Teacher Efficacy in India & Japan

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The purpose of this study is to examine how the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes works on teacher efficacy and impacts students in Japan and India. There were 661 teachers in Japan and 306 teachers in India. There were two stages. First, a confirmatory factor analysis of the "WISC-IV Guidance of Inclusive Education in Regular Classes: W-IVGIER" scale was administered in Japan and India. Second, a simultaneous multi-group analysis was conducted to examine the differences and similarities between the countries. The results showed that the teachers in India were more likely than their Japanese counterparts to report from "Understanding and consideration of the family environment," "Understanding students and forming a learning group," and "Personal teaching efficacy," was significantly higher. Japanese teachers had a greater variance in "Personal teaching efficacy," and "General educational efficacy," than their Indian counterparts. The results showed that Indian teachers' efficacy in inclusive education in the regular classroom increased when they worked with parents to understand and educate students, while Japanese teachers may need assistance to support their efficacy.

Keywords: regular classes, inclusive education, educational guidance, teacher efficacy, Japanese teacher, Indian teacher

Inclusive Education

Improving the academic performance of students and promoting inclusive education is important in today's educational world. Nowadays, the way the teachers teach has changed. The purpose of this study is to examine how the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes affects teachers' effectiveness in Japan and India, and how effective inclusive education impacts students. In this study, we define educational guidance of inclusive education as a teaching method that considers the cognitive characteristics of students who need special education. Thus, educational guidance in regular classes can take into consideration students' cognitive abilities especially the one's needing special education.

In 1994, the Declaration of Salamanca was adopted in Salamanca, Spain, as the Principles for Special Needs Education. The term "schools for all" was emphasized as a principle of inclusion or integration. In other

words, this means providing learning support for all people, including not only those with developmental disabilities, but also those with economic difficulties and children whose mother tongues are different. In recent years, UNESCO, OECD, and WHO have been leading the way in providing support for children with special needs, called Special Needs Education, throughout the world. Special-needs education is the practice of educating students in a way that addresses their individual differences and special needs. Even in the regular classroom, teachers need to make accommodations and adjustments for everyone, regardless of disability, if they do not impose a heavy burden.

Japan and India: Their Education Policies

According to Japan's Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (2012), elementary and middle school students with learning and behavioral difficulties are enrolled in regular classes at a rate of 6.5%, which may include students with developmental disabilities.

Japanese societies and test publishers are offering workshops for interpreting test results and recommending teaching methods. Therefore, psychologists and teachers continue to work well together for comprehensive assessments. Psychologists administer intelligence tests and teachers may administer academic achievement tests. Both collect ecological information, such as children's interactions in the classroom. One of the strengths of Japanese education is that there are many teachers certified as special education specialists, school psychologists, or clinical developmental psychologists who can administer individualized tests and interpret the results to better plan instruction (Ishikuma, Matsuda, Fujita, Ueno, 2016 p5).

In India, the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA, the National Primary Education Perfection Scheme) was completed in 2001. This aims to ensure that all children between the ages of 6 and 14 years are enrolled in and complete eight years of schooling (primary and higher primary). Subsequently, two laws, the Action Plan for Inclusive Education of Children and Youth with Disabilities, 2005, and the Right to Education Act, 2010, were enacted (Ministry of Social Affairs, Justice and Empowerment [MHRD], 2010). In India, the term disability is used interchangeably with special educational needs (SEN; Hodkinson & Devarakonda, 2009; Singal, 2005). At the policy level, much progress has been made in the last few years, but the practical aspects of implementation have largely been absent (Srivastava, De Boer, & Pijl, 2015). Hayashi (2019) also reports that differences in education are a factor in the intra-urban/rural disparities in household consumption expenditure, and in particular, expanding and improving the quantity and quality of education will help to reduce the disparities in the country. The role of teachers in India is significant. In addition, the rate at which students in India remain until the end of primary education has increased from 66% (2003-2008) to 82% (2011-2016) (UNICEF, 2017). However, the government can check whether the schools that provided primary education in India exist, of they do are they safe and accessible for students (UNICEF, 2004).

Inclusive Education and Teachers

Materials and environments that aim to be accessible to as many people as possible are called as a universal design. It is an effective teaching methodology to improve the learning process for all students (Capp, 2017). However, its impact on educational outcomes has not been proven (Capp, 2017). Teachers are in a highly demanding profession as they work to meet the diverse learning needs of their students. As a result, many teachers experience high levels of stress that can lead to burnout and, unfortunately, many teachers leave the profession (Gray, Wilcox, & Nordstokke, 2017). Previous studies have failed to focus on how factors of educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes affect students' learning (teaching) and teachers' efficacy. A major challenge is to embed the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes to improve students' learning and teachers' efficacy.

The Two Potencies of Teachers

Teachers played a central role in the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes (Srivastava, De Boer, & Pijl, 2015). This has a significant impact on teachers; self-efficacy is an individual's perception of their confidence in their ability to succeed in the actions required to complete a particular task (Bandura, 1997); Sense of teacher effect is their beliefs about their ability to bring about effectiveness (Ashton, 1985). "Personal teaching efficacy," refers to teachers' expectations of effectiveness in relation to their personal teaching, and "General teaching efficacy," refers to expectations of effectiveness as they relate to education in general (Gibson & Dembo, 1984). "If students are not disciplined at home, they will not accept any discipline," indicate "General teaching efficacy". "When I really try, I can get through with most difficult students," indicate "Personal teaching efficacy". Both are positively correlated, but the load is different (Gibson & Dembo, 1984). Furthermore, they are positively correlated with the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes.

Cognitive Support-based Educational Guidance

In the regular classroom, students with low verbal skills are encouraged to learn by experience or by utilizing their non-verbal skills, as well as other skills. Conversely, students with low visual ability and high verbal ability are given verbal explanations. These are done with the teacher's understanding of the characteristics of cognition. A theory that advances the understanding of children's cognition is the WISC theory. With the development of cognitive psychology, the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-Third Edition (WISC-IV) has been used worldwide by schools, educational psychologists, and practitioners as a test of intelligence in children. The validity of the Kaufman Assessment Battery for Children (K-ABC) has also been clearly demonstrated. Previous studies have suggested that the WISC index suggests characteristics of children's cognition (Saklofske, Prifitera, Weiss, Rolffhus, & Zhu, 2005; Flanagan & Kaufman, 2009; Benito, Moro & Alonso, 2009). It can also be used in educational instruction (Kaufman, Raiford & Coalson, 2016; Laurie, 2015). We believe that the use of WISC theory in educational instruction can promote inclusive education that takes into account a variety of cognitions. Furthermore, we believe that the inclusion of the plans and methods of difficult instruction in regular lessons as specified in the Ministry of Education's Guidelines for Learning and Guidance (2017) will be accurate as educational guidance. In the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes, teachers are important for providing cognitive support to students. We believe that such an impact is "Personal teaching efficacy".

Teacher Consideration of the Family Environment

Teachers need to take into account the student's home environment, such as the amount of work and the retention of knowledge, in order to promote learning. In particular, inclusive education requires the understanding of the students' parents as well as friends. Parents

and teachers need to be involved in a variety of support activities, especially for students. Flexibility based on the teacher's understanding of the child would allow for the development of more inclusive teaching methods and the adoption of a variety of learning styles, shifting the emphasis from teacher-centered to child-centered (UNICEF, 2013). Therefore, in the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes, teachers who pay attention to the family environment are believed to have a "Personal teaching efficacy". This will affect the diverse resources required for inclusive education. Educational guidance goes beyond the factors of genetics, and teachers provide guidance.

Understanding Students and Forming a Learning Group

For students who have difficulty in concentrating, weak language comprehension and have a strong resistance to interpersonal relationships, teachers need to devise ways to get them to participate in learning. For example, if a student shows difficulties in learning, they should ask other students to explain concepts in their own words, which enhances understanding for students who have a weak comprehension. Vygotsky (1935) pointed out the most proximal region of development and the importance of learning among children. Cohen, Kulin & Kulink (1982) and Goodlad & Hirst (1990) pointed out the importance of peer-tutoring among students, including trained tutors, which means that learners learn by helping and teaching each other. It is a series of interactions. In the regular classroom, there are a variety of students. It is important for the teacher not only to provide individualized instruction but also to develop group learning among the students. The teacher usually assigns the role of explainer and learner to the learners in the regular classroom and carries out activities that allow students to learn from each other. In fact, it has been shown that when students are taught the skills of explanation and questioning, they form a learning group and their performance on post comprehension tests improved (King, Staffieri, & Adalgais, 1998). Palincsar & Brown

(1984) reported that under teacher's guidance, students with reading difficulties learned to read more effectively with the use of effective reading strategies (summarizing, questioning, clarifying, and predicting) and the encouragement of group interaction. Therefore, it is necessary for teachers to form learning groups in regular classes to understand the abilities and personalities of individual students in order to increase the effectiveness of their learning. In the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes, teachers who understand the students and form a learning group have an impact on the "Personal teaching efficacy".

Team Assistance with Diverse Professionals

Students with special needs have various education and life outcomes (Wagner, Blackorby, Cameto, & Newman, 1993). School counselors already provide emotional and social support and intervention for students who need special education (Yoshikawa, Tiarks, Kehle, & Bray, 2019). Teachers are seen as key players in implementing inclusive education (Srivastava, Boer, & Pijl, 2015). However, the educational guidance of inclusive education is not clear. The specific measure of the problem is important from the perspective of prevention and intervention practices (Van Schalkwyk, 2019). Once the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes is revealed, it makes it easier for teachers, school counselors, assistants, and welfare and medical practitioners to understand the factors concerning students with special needs. This encourages collaboration between teachers, school counselors, assistants, welfare and medical practitioners, and researchers.

The Present Study

The purpose of this study is to examine how the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes works on teacher efficacy and effective inclusive education for students in Japan and India. This study had two stages. We conducted a confirmatory factor analysis of the "WISC-IV Guidance of Inclusive Education in Regular Classes: W-IVGIER" scale in Japan and India. Later, a simultaneous multi-group analysis

was conducted to examine the differences and similarities between the countries. A comparison of the inclusive teaching and learning and instructional scales in the two countries reveals the challenges of teachers in both countries and helps to improve inclusive teaching and teacher efficacy. We also think that it will help reduce the factors of teacher's stress. The Japanese W-IVGIER scale has already been completed and is shown in Appendix 1 (Ishikawa, Matsumoto, 2020).

Method

Japanese Research Participants

Questionnaire surveys and Internet-based questionnaire surveys were conducted with 980 public elementary school teachers in the Kyushu, Kinki, and Tokai regions. In Japan, there are nine districts. All the school boards of each district were requested to participate in the survey, which was approved by all three districts. These districts showed moderate academic ability in the children's academic ability survey and were considered appropriate as sample data for teaching instruction. About 661 teachers (response rate: 67.5%) answered the questionnaire and completed the survey; these results were used in the analysis (male: 316, female: 329, unpublished: Mean age was 16: 48.8, and standard deviation: 14.4). All the teachers were Japanese nationals. The number and ratio of teachers with fewer than ten years of experience are 118 (17.9%), 158 (23.9%) with 10 to 19 years of experience, 151 (22.8%) with 20 to 29 years of experience, and 234 (35.4%) with 30 years or more of experience (Table 1). In Japan, private elementary schools account for 1.2% (Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, 2019), thus we chose a public elementary school. The percentage by experience shows the demographics and uniformity of Japanese teachers in Table 1.

Indian Research Participants

We selected 184 (60%) public elementary school teachers, and 122 (40%) private elementary school teachers, which matches the proportion of primary schools in India (District Information System for Education, 2015). 176

Table 1. Number and percentage of participants by age

Japan		India	
experience in years	n ()=%	experience in years	n ()=%
less -9	118 (17.9)	less than 4	30 (9.80)
10-19	158 (23.9)	14 -9	86 (28.10)
20-29	151 (22.8%)	10-19	70 (22.88)
30+	234 (35.4%)	20-29	76 (24.84%)
		30+	44 (14.38%)
Total	661		306

women and 130 men were selected, matching the gender ratio of Indian elementary school teachers. Their average age was 32.9 years. Table 1 shows the hierarchical distribution of the teacher experience of the research participants. As far as we investigated, the age structure of Indian elementary school teachers was unknown. There are research participant schools in three states of India such as Puducherry, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka. The literacy rate in these three states is the same as the average literacy rate in India (Government of India Human Resources Development Department, 2018).

Procedure

We carried out the Japanese surveys from April to December 2018. We carried out the Indian survey from July to August 2019. We explained the study's objectives to the principals of the education committee and the schools, which are: (a) participation in the surveys was voluntary, (b) the answers would not be used for purposes other than research, and (c) the participants' privacy would be protected. A similar explanation was given on the questionnaire form and the opening page of the Internet survey. The teachers completed the questionnaire without time constraints or imposing exclusion criteria for the participants. Also, this study was approved by Pondicherry University (2019). SPSS Amoss 21.0 was used for the analysis.

Usage Scale

W-IVGIER Scale: Used the items created by Ishikawa and Matsumoto (2018); these items were created for educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes based on the impressions of students of teacher training. This will be described in detail.

Ishikawa and Matsumoto (2018) have given a lecture on WISC-IV's intelligence theory and educational guidance to students of a second-year teacher training course. We referred to the WISC-IV index (Wechsler & Japanese WISC-IV Publication Committee, 2010; Ueno, Matsuda, Kobayashi, & Kinoshita, 2015). We also explained the plans and methods for guiding the difficulty level in regular classes defined in the Courses of Study (Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, 2017).

Subsequently, we had students of a second-year teacher training course think of an educational guidance plan for elementary school having home economics class for children with low scores in the four indexes (verbal comprehension, perceptual reasoning, working memory, and processing speed). Considering the lectures, the students in the teacher training course created an educational guidance plan and carried out a mock lesson. We then asked them to write down items that should be considered for the learning of children with difficulties enrolled in regular classes in the form of free descriptions, and based on the answers, we created 120 items that we thought were necessary.

Items selection: Two graduate students in the field of education-one elementary school teacher in their 40s and one graduate teacher-reviewed the contents of the items and corrected their expressions. Items that lacked generality and duplicated content were excluded, expressions of some items were modified, and, finally, we had 27 items. The English version of the question items of the W-IVGIER was created based on the agreement of one graduate student whose native language is Japanese, a graduate student whose native language is English, and two university teachers. Same procedure was

followed for the Japanese version of the question items.

Hypothesis 1: Compared with Japanese teachers, Indian teachers may have a stronger influence on their personal effectiveness by “Understanding and consideration of the family environment,” and “Understanding students and forming a learning group”. The reason is that in India, the most privileged children are about six times more likely to acquire basic reading, writing, and computing skills than girls in the poorest households with uneducated parents (UNICEF, 2016).

Scale for Teachers’ Sense of Efficacy: Furthermore, we believed to have positive correlations with W-IVGIER scale. We used nine items on personal teaching efficacy and six items on W-IVGIER scale of teachers’ sense of efficacy by Gibson & Dembo (1984). For Japanese teachers, Sakurai’s (1992) translation of the Teacher Effectiveness Scale from Gibson & Dembo (1984) was used. The Sakurai version also examined the validity of W-IVGIER scale. We asked the respondents to provide answers ranging from (1) “I don’t think so at all” to (5) “I very much think so. “

Hypothesis 2: Japanese teachers have a greater variance in “Personal teaching efficacy” and “General educational efficacy” than Indian teachers. The reason is that the proportion of Japanese elementary teachers who have a high self-affirmation and self-efficacy to increase motivation for learning is low (OECD, 2019a).

Results

1. Comparison of Scales

Examination of the Factor Structure: First, a confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to verify the equality of the W-IVGIER scale and the teacher efficacy scale for Japan and India. The individual analysis was performed to see the fitness of the four-factor model (“Understanding students and forming a learning group,” “Small steps and devising ways of reading,” “Being creative with viewpoints, prospects, and steps,” and “Understanding and consideration of the family environment,” and the two factors of “Personal teaching efficacy,” and “General teaching efficacy”). The W-IVGIER scale has a slightly lower fit in Japan with CFI.953, RMSEA.055, and SRMR.050 than in India where the fit is more: CFI.947, RMSEA.050, and SRMR.044. However, the model fits both the countries - Japan and India. “Teacher efficacy scale,” is CFI.810, RMSEA.106, and SRMR.083 in Japan and CFI.824, RMSEA.080, and SRMR.076 in India, and both Japan and India have a slightly higher degree of compliance. The model was shown to be a good fit. This allowed us to determine that a six-factor structure, which can be considered a factor load as conceptualized in the W-IVGIER scale and the teacher efficacy scale, is acceptable. We also conducted a factor-by-factor t-test for two populations in Japan and India (Table 2). Among the six factors, “Understanding students and forming a learning group,” was significantly higher in Japan, and the other factors were significantly higher in India.

Table 2. factor thing t-test

Subfactors	Japan	India	t value
1. General educational efficacy	2.705(.668)	4.009***(.580)	24.715
2. Personal teaching efficacy	2.854(.612)	3.670***(.663)	15.039
3. Understanding students and forming a learning group	4.209*(.534)	4.107(.634)	-2.037
4. Small steps and devising ways of reading	3.954(.620)	4.192***(.677)	4.266
5. Being creative with viewpoints, prospects, and steps	3.908(.665)	4.131***(.778)	3.508
6. Understanding and consideration of the family environment	3.688(.734)	4.140***(.786)	6.948

Note. Japan N = 661, India N = 308 , Upper row: M, (): SD, ***p < .001, **p < .01, * p < .05.

Table 3. Subfactors for Japanese and India Teachers' Educational Guidance of Inclusive Education in Regular Classes and Correlation of Teachers' Beliefs, Personal Teaching Efficacy, and General Teaching Efficacy

		India					
	1	2	3	4	5	6.	
1	-	.059**	.511**	.487**	.321**	.525**	
2	.571**	-	.605**	.431**	.263**	.578**	
3	.433**	.545**	-	.375**	.256**	.547**	
4	.582**	.458**	.354**	-	.344**	.397**	
5	.215**	.266**	.256**	.198**	-	.407**	
6	.078	.130*	.096	.116	.394**	-	
Japan							

Note. * $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, Japan $N=661$. India $N=301$

1. Understanding students and forming a learning group; 2. Small steps and devising ways of reading; 3. Being creative with viewpoints, prospects, and steps; 4. Understanding and consideration of the family environment, 5. Personal teaching efficacy, 6. General educational efficacy

In this section, we explain the differences in the correlations of each factor between Japan and India. Compared to Japan, India had moderately higher correlations between "General educational efficacy", "Understanding students and forming a learning group," "Small steps and devising ways of reading," "Being creative with viewpoints, prospects, and steps," "Understanding and consideration of the family environment," and " Personal teaching efficacy " respectively. There were also slightly higher

correlations between 'personal efficacy' and 'understanding pupils and creating learning groups' and 'understanding and consideration of the home environment'. Furthermore, there was little correlation between "Understanding students and forming a learning group, " and " Small steps and devising ways of reading " in India compared to Japan (Table 3).

There were differences between the two countries in each scale, thus we considered the possibility that differences in inter-scale correlations might appear. Therefore, we conducted a simultaneous multi-population analysis to determine whether there were differences in inter-scale correlations in the two countries. In the analysis, Model 1 was used as a configuration-invariant model (no equality constraint), and Models 2 - 5 were used as equality-constrained models, with the path coefficients between the factors analyzed in decreasing order (Table 4). It was found that the placement-invariant model in Model 1 fits the data better. The results are shown in Figure 1. Table 5 shows the results of inter-group comparisons of the path coefficients from Model 1. This ensures data equality between Japan and India.

Figure 1 shows the assumptions for Japan and India in Model 1. The path coefficients were from "Understanding students and forming a learning group," "Small steps and devising ways of reading," "Understanding and consideration of the family environment," "Being creative with viewpoints prospects and steps," to "Personal teaching efficacy," .08, .06, .12, and .15 for

Table 4. Adaptability index for each model

Model	X ²	SRMR	RMSEA	CFI	AIC
Model 1: No equality constraint	.000	.000	.000	1.000	42.000
Model 2: equality constraint 2←4	126.911	.168	.314	.663	158.911
Model 3: equality constraint 2←4+6	191.374	.224	.353	.487	221.374
Model 4: equality constraint 2←4+6+3	198.352	.232	.310	.473	224.352
Model 5: equality constraint 2←4+6+3+5	195.789	.228	.289	.483	67.627

Note. 1. General educational efficacy; 2. Personal teaching efficacy; 3. Understanding students and forming a learning group; 4. Small steps and devising ways of reading; 5. Being creative with viewpoints, prospects, and steps; 6. Understanding and consideration of the family environment

Figure 1. Japan and India are estimated results

Note. The two-way arrows represent covariance. **p < .01, * p < .05.

Table 5. Comparison of path coefficients between groups in Japan and India

	z	p
1↔2	4.584	.000**
→2	3.069	.002**
4→2	1.261	.207
5→2	8.491	.000**
6→2	2.839	.005**
3→4	8.289	.000**

**p < .01, * p < .05.

Japan, in that order. The path coefficients for India were .12, .15, .06, and .33, in that order. The covariance of “General educational efficacy,” and “Personal teaching efficacy,” “Understanding students and forming a learning group” and “Small steps and devising ways of reading” is .07 in Japan. The same for India were .07.

The Indian teachers were having a significant difference than Japanese teachers for “Understanding and consideration of the family environment,” “Understanding students and forming a learning group,” and “Being creative with viewpoints prospects and steps,” to “Personal teaching efficacy”. Japanese teachers had a greater variance in “Personal teaching efficacy,” and “General educational efficacy,” than their Indian counterparts.

Appendix. Results and Basic Statistics of the Analysis of Factors from the Scale for Japanese Teachers’ Educational Guidance of Inclusive Education in Regular Classes

1. Understanding students and forming a learning group
There are many different students in the class, so I try to ask the other children to be cooperative to maintain an appropriate atmosphere in the classroom.
I need to think about learning and how to understand students.
I make it conducive for the students to focus if there are children who need more attention.
I arrange the classes so that they are not directive but rather interactive in nature.
I consider the usual nature of the students.
If some questions are difficult and the students find them difficult, I would give them some hints.
2. Small steps and devising ways of reading
I clearly read out to them the information and its various aspects.
To facilitate learning, I do it in small steps.
I prepare the contents of activities from basic to complicated ones for students to have various experiences.
3. Being creative with viewpoints, prospects, and steps

I use visual techniques to help children learn.
I use figures and worksheets.
I introduce the procedures and techniques for learning in such a way that it can be seen from far.
I show some figures and lists for them to understand the ideas and procedures.
4. Understanding and consideration of the family environment
I encourage the learning process not only in their school life but also in their family life.
I consider their family environment.
I encourage the students to have conversations at home.

Discussion

Educational Guidance of Inclusive Education in Regular Classes

The present study reveals the reality of educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes in India and Japan. It was found that teachers' "Understanding students and forming a learning group," "Small steps and devising ways of reading," "Being creative with viewpoints, prospects, and steps," "Understanding and consideration of the family environment," is important. Japan has always been at the top of PISA in terms of academic achievement surveys (OECD, 2019b). The results are considered to be of some benefit. These findings will be useful.

India

Teachers in India need to work with parents and other professionals for the sake of the child. Teachers in India must also understand and take into account the child's home environment. Without cooperation of the family, "Personal teaching efficacy," will not increase. Teachers in India may lose their teaching efficacy if they do not collaborate with students' families. Hence, teachers believe that the educational guidance of inclusive education in regular classes will be facilitated by collaboration with parents, where schools are a safe place for teachers to educate students while understanding them. Primary teachers, in particular, are the foundation for this.

They would be responsible not only for individual rewards but also for the development of the country. As a result, we believe that children will attend school, graduate and learn better. Similarly, without "Understanding students and forming learning groups," "Personal teaching efficacy" will not improve. We also believe that student learning will be enhanced by these practices.

Japan

In terms of classroom discipline and learning atmosphere, Japan shows good results, for example, the percentage of teachers who "lose a lot of time due to students disrupting the class," is the lowest in elementary school among OECD participating countries (OECD, 2019a). The factor means that inclusive teaching and education instruction were significantly lower for Japanese teachers than for Indian teachers, except for "Understanding students and forming a learning group". Japanese teachers not only teach children with understanding but also teach them how to live their lives. On the other hand, the Japanese teachers were significantly lower in "Personal teaching efficacy," and "General educational efficacy," than the Indian teachers. In other words, Japanese teachers provide not only educational guidance but also life guidance, not only to individuals but also to groups. As a result, many teachers have a low sense of efficacy. School counselors need to work to support not only the students but teachers as well. We believe that by supporting the individual teachers, each teacher is supported, and the students learning improves. To promote inclusive education in the regular classroom, school counselors may be necessary.

Future Challenges

Unlike special-needs classrooms, regular classrooms may have a large number of teachers with diverse students, and they may be using the four factors as adaptive learning guidance. It is necessary to study the implementation of the W-IVGIER scale in regular classrooms in order to examine its effects on students. In addition, team assistance with various specialists is also necessary. A study of student-teacher change

in the implementation of the W-IVGIER scale by teachers with the participation of diverse experts will also be necessary. Problems can be measured and preventive interventions can be made. Similar studies outside of Japan and India would reveal and improve the reality of the impact of inclusive teaching and learning instruction and teacher efficacy in regular classrooms.

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